

ISSN 2181 - 7286

2/2024

ТАЪЛИМ ТИЗИМИДА ИЖТИМОЙ-ГУМАНИТАР ФАНЛАР

ISSN 2181-7286
2/2024

Таълим тизимида ижтимоий-гуманитар фанлар

Тошкент – 2024

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Журнал Ўзбекистон матбуот ва ахборот агентлиги томонидан рўйхатга олинган, 2007 йил 22 январь, № 0205 сонли гувоҳнома

ISSN 2181-7286. Иқтисод бўлими ОАК рўйхатига 2019 йил 1 январдан, Педагогика бўлими 2019 йил 29 июндан, Тарих, Фалсафа, Психология бўлимлари 2022 йил 30 ноябрдан, киритилган.

Журнал зарегистрирован Узбекским агентством по печати и информации 22 января 2007 года, свидетельство № 0205

ISSN 2181-7286. С 1 января 2019 г. журнал включен в перечень ВАК экономического отдела, с 29 июня 2019 г. – в перечень отдела педагогики, с 30 ноября 2022 г. – в перечень отделов истории, философии и психологии.

The journal was registered by the Press and Information Agency of Uzbekistan, January 22, 2007, certificate No. 0205

ISSN 2181-7286. The part of of Economy has been included in the list of Higher Attestation Committee since January 1, 2019, the part of Pedagogy since June 29, 2019, and the parts of History, Philosophy, and Psychology since November 30, 2022.

THE MAIN GOAL OF THE ACTIVITY OF THE PEDAGOGICAL EDUCATIONAL CLUSTER TO IMPROVE THE PROFESSIONAL TRAINING OF FUTURE ENGINEERS.

BO‘LAJAK MUXANDISLAR KASBIY TAYYORGARLIGINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISHDA PEDAGOGIK TA‘LIM KLASTERI FAOLIYATINING ASOSIY MAQSADI.

ОСНОВНАЯ ЦЕЛЬ ДЕЯТЕЛЬНОСТИ ПЕДАГОГИЧЕСКОГО ОБРАЗОВАТЕЛЬНОГО КЛАСТЕРА ПО СОВЕРШЕНСТВОВАНИЮ ПРОФЕССИОНАЛЬНОЙ ПОДГОТОВКИ БУДУЩИХ ИНЖЕНЕРОВ.

Sirojiddinova I.M. (Andijan Machine-Building Institute,
Head of the Department of Humanities,
Candidate of Pedagogical Sciences, Associate Professor)

This article will discuss the determination of the main possible directions for designing a methodological teaching system in the theory of pedagogical technologies, the main goal of the activity of the pedagogical educational cluster, the requirement of integrity, and all the basic laws of the educational process.

Key words: Pedagogical technology, methodological system, cluster of pedagogical education, integrity, educational process.

Ushbu maqolada pedagogik texnologiyalar nazariyasida o‘qitishning metodik tizimini loyihalashtirishning asosiy mumkin bo‘lgan yo‘nalishlarini aniqlash, pedagogik ta‘lim klasteri faoliyatining asosiy maqsadi, yaxlitlik talabi, o‘quv jarayonining barcha asosiy qonuniyatlari haqida fikr yuritiladi.

Kalit so‘zlar: Pedagogik texnologiya, metodik tizim, pedagogik ta‘lim klasteri, yaxlitlik, o‘quv jarayoni.

В данной статье речь пойдет об определении основных возможных направлений проектирования методической системы обучения в теории педагогических технологий, основной цели деятельности педагогического образовательного кластера, требовании целостности, всех основных закономерностях образовательного процесса.

Ключевые слова: Педагогическая технология, методическая система, кластер педагогического образования, целостность, образовательный процесс.

In the theory of pedagogical technologies, project activity is considered as an innovative type of professional competence of a modern teacher, and in the context of the implementation of the state educational standard, this activity becomes a qualitatively new form of organization of the educational process. According to the general algorithm of project activity, the first stage involves determining the main possible directions of designing a methodological training system. Such areas can be considered as reform, modernization, or simply reducing the hours of training sessions. At the second stage, it is necessary to reveal a pedagogically conceived or planned idea of project activity in the form of a concept. At the

third stage, this concept requires a clear goal statement, the creation of a process diagram and the definition of the principles of its implementation.

In educational cluster technology, each specialist must take into account the interests of the educational subject. The private interests of all subjects of education ultimately serve the common good. Mutual control - this principle means that the activities of educational subjects united within the framework of cluster technology are interdependent. An error or deficiency in one subject affects performance in a second subject. Thus, within the cluster, educational subjects whose activities are connected with each other form a mutual system. The main goal of the teacher education cluster is:

- ensure effective continuity in the field of pedagogy and promote the best students into the teaching profession;

- conducting professional training of teachers based on practice and promptly providing feedback from interested parties;

- creating an environment for training future education specialists based on practices with innovative experience;

- reducing the time required for young specialists to acquire professional skills;

- creation of a new generation of educational, educational, methodological, scientific literature, manuals and didactic materials in teacher education;

- increase the scientific, scientific and pedagogical potential of teacher education;

- integration of intellectual resources around current problems in the development of teacher education;

- find different forms and types of education, science and pedagogical practice and apply them in education;

- improving mechanisms to ensure the integrity of education and training;

- create the opportunity to quickly restore connections with preschool, school and higher educational institutions and other applicants for the training of teaching staff;

- scientific substantiation of the need for communication, communication and cooperation between units of teacher education.

Based on these goals, the innovation cluster of teacher education solves the following tasks:

- training of teaching staff with modern knowledge and qualifications for educational institutions in the region;

- effective use of innovative pedagogical technologies in improving the quality of education;

- consistent establishment of scientific activities in the field of pedagogy;

- ensuring the integrity and continuity of the content of the main (textbook) and auxiliary (dictionaries, dictionaries, electronic resources, etc.) teaching aids at all stages of training;

- in order to fill the gaps in the level of knowledge of teachers of general education institutions in the region, organize temporary advanced training courses together with the department of public education of the region;

- organize scientific and practical seminars together with the regional public education department in order to eliminate problems associated with teaching subjects in secondary schools;

- strengthen scientific cooperation with research institutes, scientific centers and basic higher education institutions in order to increase the scientific potential of university professors and teachers and future talented engineers;

attract future engineers and teachers with the ability to conduct scientific research to secondary schools;

conducting internships at a leading foreign university in order to acquire advanced foreign experience in the field of pedagogy.[1, 2].

Project activities, which are the technological component of our research, are built according to the structure proposed by researcher V.M. Monakhov, and includes the most important component - methodological system management [3, 4] and is the sum of these descriptions. A very important role is played by the requirement of integrity, which consists in determining an element of the educational process, which in project activities can have the two named qualities. The requirement of completeness is interpreted as follows: an element of the educational process model, characterized by all parameters, can be considered as a design object. On the one hand, the educational process determines the minimum part that satisfies the requirement of integrity, and on the other hand, all the basic laws of the educational process are manifested in it. Finally, the technological legitimacy of the model requires strict expression and systematic organization of didactic information in the learning process.

The study by Sh. K. Mardonov provides comments on the innovative cluster approach in education [5, 6]. Based on the listed patterns of modeling pedagogical objects, we identified three main objects: a curriculum, a trajectory of professional training for a future engineer, and a methodological training system. Systematization of the most common design technologies allows us to draw a fundamental conclusion: it is advisable to shift the center of gravity of optimization from design activities to create the three listed pedagogical objects to the fourth object - didactic conditions. It is the optimization of didactic conditions that makes it possible to implement the projects of pedagogical objects listed above.

(see Table 1):

The main stages of complex design of pedagogical objects.

№	Stages	Contents of the stages
1.	Stage 1	In order to determine the significance of individual educational elements of the educational program in pedagogy, the structural elements of the work program are sorted using the expert method. This qualimetric approach allows us to ensure the content validity of the educational process in relation to the state educational standard.
2.	Stage 2	Using the cluster approach, the working field of design activity in the educational space is determined by calculating the level of interaction between the various structural elements of the curriculum. In this case, the workspace is not only a response to the existence of certain subjects of the educational space, but also an expression of the pedagogical properties of this space.
3.	Stage 3	Based on the degree of interaction of the structural elements of the pedagogy curriculum with each other and with the structural elements of other academic subjects, a curriculum for the educational institution will be developed, providing a trajectory for the professional training of the future engineer.
4.	Stage 4	By producing didactic and diagnostic-qualimetric support for the curriculum, it will be possible to create a motivational and methodological training system and achieve a guaranteed level of professional competence of a specialist.

We consider the trajectory of professional training of future engineers from the point of view of design technology. In relation to vocational education, three pedagogical objects, complex design technology should be considered as a set, and its goals are:

educational program in pedagogical sciences;
 trajectory of professional training of future engineers;
 methodological system of training in the conditions of vocational education.

Using certain technological methods, we begin to develop models of each pedagogical object. Based on the expert method and the cluster sampling method of forming a workspace for project activities, the main stages of curriculum design are identified. The listed courses are aimed at building a trajectory for the professional training of future engineers not only in accordance with the purpose of the study, but also with the concept of “educational trajectory,” which implies the working area of project activity.

Designing the professional training trajectory of future engineers requires the creation of its model. Let us list the main stages of the integrated design of educational facilities.

According to modern pedagogical methodology, the work area of designing the professional training trajectory of future engineers is the result of the perception of the degree of interaction of the structural elements of the curriculum. It is impossible to imagine an optimal educational trajectory that is not associated with the categorization of the educational process and its methodological support. An exception can occur in a process where the intended result occurs by chance. However, the student is always in an educational environment that creates conditions for the learning process and interacts with other subjects of the educational space. Consequently, when constructing the professional training trajectory of future engineers, there cannot be an element of chance. A single conclusion about the cause-and-effect relationship between the workspace of project activity and the resulting consequence - the educational trajectory - is self-evident.

The criteria for the comprehensive development of professional training of future engineers require increasing professional flexibility and mobility of the future specialist in accordance with the purpose, time and content (see Figure 1)

Figure 1. Criteria for the comprehensive development of professional training for future engineers

Researcher A. A. Listvin defined from scientific and educational clusters to educational space. In pedagogical research, a comprehensive model for the design of

pedagogical objects was developed based on the random sampling method [7]. Based on the principle of discreteness, the law of integrity, which emphasizes the inclusion of a large number of structural elements in the educational process, it is possible to classify an exemplary curriculum that reflects the requirements of the state educational standard in pedagogical subjects. In the curriculum, not only a high level of content significance can be important for structural elements that differ in their logical conclusion, but also for the structural elements of the educational topic, department and discipline.

In educational cluster technology, each specialist must take into account the interests of the educational subject. The private interests of all subjects of education ultimately serve the common good. If the structural elements of the program are indivisible structural units of educational elements that can be sorted, then educational topics combine several structural elements, are part of a certain section of the program and consistently reveal its content. On the other hand, educational topics are combined into one within one subject, but can form sections that differ from each other in the area of study or in the method of describing the object of study.

Based on the analysis of the features of the structural organization of the curriculum, we considered the structural element to be the smallest unit of selection when designing the educational process, but it can be noted that the subject of the study should be considered the Main unit of selection. Using the obvious advantages of this approach and its methodological basis, the teacher can develop a work program that is considered a necessary condition for achieving a guaranteed level of professional competence.

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